

HIV and Mental Health: A Three-Phased Program Development Study in the Philippines

Maria Isabel E. Melgar

Ateneo Bulatao Center for Psychological Services, Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines

Chester B. Alejandro

Ateneo Bulatao Center for Psychological Services, Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines

Ariana Denise A. Dee

Ateneo Bulatao Center for Psychological Services, Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines

Abstract

A three-phased study and program development on HIV and Mental Health were conducted for a period of two years. This study encompasses a baseline survey of mental health issues among people living with HIV (PLHIV), the design and development of virtual learning modules on mental health and HIV for health providers, and a pre-implementation qualitative study on the delivery of online modules to target health workers. The results of the quantitative survey reveal moderately high self-reported depression, anxiety, and suicide ideation among patients with HIV. After the survey, topics for e-modules on mental health were identified including self-help modules for health workers. These mental health modules were consolidated with modules pertaining to HIV treatment. A qualitative study on the acceptability and feasibility of the use of the e-modules was conducted by interviewing health workers from different HIV treatment and care sites. Significant insights into the learning experiences among health workers gave researchers a deeper understanding of the cognitive acceptance and resistance towards virtual and self-paced modules.

Keywords: *Mental Health and HIV; Self-help Modules; Health Workers.*

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Introduction

The Philippines has the fastest-growing HIV epidemic in the Asia and the Pacific region with a 237% increase in annual new HIV infections from 2010-2020 (Department of Health Philippines (DOH), 2021). The HIV population is primarily composed of young adults ages 25-34 accounting for 52% of the total recorded cases. Generally, these individuals are highly at risk for mental health issues such as

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depression and anxiety which can affect treatment adherence and other health outcomes (Mayston et al., 2012).

In the Philippines, some gaps need to be addressed to have a better quality of life and improved well-being among PLHIV. According to UNAIDS (2020), assessing the Philippine's response to the HIV epidemic, one of the comments is the need to develop integrated care where other concerns such as mental health issues are addressed. This poses a need for mental health professionals and competency in basic strategies to address mental health concerns.

There are approximately 1400 psychologists and 500 psychiatrists or a ratio of 1 mental health professional for 80,000 individuals (Manila Times, 2021). The shortage of mental health professionals is further exacerbated by the geographical nature of the Philippines with several islands, causing difficulties in accessing these professionals who are mainly concentrated in city centers. In addition, the consultation fees of mental health professionals may be steep for a typical working Filipino. Another big problem is that health care providers in HIV clinics, do not have essential academic and professional training in mental health.

Meanwhile, there has been a rise in the use of technology for e-learning especially during the pandemic period which was a great opportunity for health workers to catch up. More specifically, asynchronous learning management systems are popularly used by educational institutions to deliver course content to people worldwide. These systems “use forum and chat functions, document repositories, or videos and recorded footage of webinars that can be watched on demand.” (Ebner & Gegenfurtner, 2019). In its purest form, “participants view video-lectures or read texts and training independently. Sometimes additional written tasks and quizzes are added to solidify knowledge gain.” (Soll et al. 2021.). Advantages of this mode of learning include: (a) flexibility in both location and time, (b) standardization of key content, ensuring participants equally receive high-quality instruction, (c) opportunities for equal participation, and (d) reinforcement of agentic learning due to its accessibility (Clarke et al. 2004; Ebner & Gegenfurtner, 2019; Kaufmann et al., 2021; Puzziferro & Shelton, 2008; Soll et al. 2021).

All these international developments have benefited our health workers around the country. The pandemic has ignited the interest and focus around mental health and these were reflected in the numerous master classes, webinars and recorded lectures that were accessible everywhere in the world. Independent and asynchronous learning emerged as among the most popular learning mode.

Several studies found asynchronous learning environments to be relatively effective alternatives. For example, Olson and colleagues' 2021 study showed the transition to online learning of evidence-based school mental health prices resulted not only to a wider reach of audience but is comparable to a hybrid format in terms of trainees' satisfaction and impact. Moreover, students' support systems (i.e. families and caregivers) were found to have gained more knowledge, resulting in more positive behaviors after participating in a virtual youth suicide prevention training (Olson et al., 2021). Another study by Soll and colleagues (2021) found asynchronous, blended, and inverted-classroom online learning environments for cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) training to be non-inferior compared to its counterpart. Despite the small effect in favor of in-person training in terms of active participation and professional benefit, participants' satisfaction “with the online courses were not relevantly lower in the categories information content, conception of content, didactic presentation,

satisfaction with the trainer as a suitable role-model, working atmosphere, own commitment, and practical relevance than satisfaction with the in-person training courses.” (Soll et al., 2021). This makes online learning a feasible and practical alternative whenever there are scarce resources to deliver in-person training (Soll et al., 2021).

Given the current state of HIV in a resource-poor country, there is a dire need to develop the competencies and capacities of healthcare providers handling complex problems of PLHIVs. The scarce and stressed HIV primary care providers should be consistently supported through training and self-care strategies to sustain a positive and healing environment in treatment hubs and health centers.

Materials and Methods

This is a study that employed a mixed method approach.

It is a three-phased project where Phase 1 involves a quantitative survey on the mental health and well-being of people with HIV; Phase 2 is the development of virtual modules on mental health and HIV; and Phase 3 is a pre-implementation qualitative study on the acceptability of virtual modules.

Phase 1: Survey of Mental Health

The survey on mental health was administered to 287 male and female adult PLHIV in 2023. They were residing in five regions in the country at the time of the study. Of the total respondents, 92% were males. The mean age of respondents was 32.35 years. All were undergoing ART treatment for HIV. The average years of living with HIV is 4.38 years.

The survey instrument was written in both English and Filipino languages. The instrument is a battery of brief scales that measure depression, anxiety, suicide intentions, stigma, perceived social support, trauma, and resilience. The instrument employed a Likert scale with different ranges (from 3 to 7) depending on the specific variables being measured. The English scales were translated into Filipino. This was pre-tested by recruiting four HIV participants to go through the cultural adaptation protocol. Their comments and suggestions were noted to improve the comprehensibility of the instrument.

After consenting to join the study, all respondents were given the option to choose which language they were more comfortable in answering the questionnaire. The survey administration was conducted in close collaboration with peer counselors working in treatment hubs or social hygiene clinics that participated in the study. The survey was self-administered.

Phase 2: Development of Virtual Modules

After Phase 1, the results of the survey helped identify mental health-related issues and HIV-related topics that could be the focus of modules to be developed. Originally, all modules were asynchronous and intended to be offered to individual learners on demand.

The modules were conceptualized and crafted with notable experts who specialized in the identified topics. As such, experts from institutions such as a center for psychological services, a psychology department in 2 universities, an AIDS Clinic and

medical research institute, AIDS Society of the Philippines, and a university in San Diego, USA were engaged in Phase 2.

Phase 3: Pre-Implementation of Virtual Modules

The objective of Phase 3 is to identify factors that will facilitate and impede the effective delivery of the modules to meet their learning outcomes. Interviews with selected health workers from different health clinics were conducted. Three peer counselors, one social worker, one HIV physician, one NGO project coordinator, and one supervisor of peer counselors were individually interviewed to seek their perceptions and their observations as potential recipients of on-demand virtual modules. The participants' background reflected long work experience in HIV treatment ranging from six years to twenty-two years as well as experience in online training during the COVID period. Prior to the interview, the interviewees received a copy of the summaries of the modules and the objectives of the study. Those who agreed signed a consent form.

Results

Phase 1

The results of the mental health screening survey showed a moderately high rate of depression, suicide ideation, and anxiety i.e., that is higher than the rates in the general population (See Table 1). The survey revealed that 43% and 41% or less than half of the HIV participants were flagged for depression and anxiety respectively. In addition, 26% were flagged for suicidal ideation. The other variables measured by the instrument have the results as follows: perceived social support with an average of 66.3 (high), 90.80 for HIV-related stigma (relatively high), and 30.15 for resilience levels (3rd quartile, high). This means that HIV infected participants of this survey felt that they were receiving adequate social support from partners, friends and families but their felt self-stigma remains high. Nevertheless, their high level of resilience have kept them strong and able to cope with HIV.

Table 1. Summary of Participants Flagged for Mental Health Issues

Mental Health Indicators Summary (N = 287)					
Depression		Anxiety		Suicidal Ideation	
With Depression	No Depression	With Anxiety	No Anxiety	With Suicidal Ideation	No Suicidal Ideation
123 (43%)	164	117 (41%)	170	74 (26%)	213

Phase 2

Four major clusters of modules were created (See Table 2 and Table 3). Each of the modules was designed to respond to the needs revealed by the survey. They were conceptualized and implemented in collaboration with a team of experts. The recorded lectures used a mix of English and Filipino languages to enhance its appeal to target audience. Each cluster is supported with a battery of learning tools such as nuggets and short quizzes.

Table 2. Four Clusters of E-Modules

<p>Cluster 1 Mental Health Survey HIV 101 HIV and Mental Health Mental Health First Aid</p> <p>Inclusion Quick Screening Tools Video Lectures Powerpoint slides Nuggets Short quiz Learning Materials and References</p>	<p>Cluster 2 Motivational Interviewing</p> <p>Inclusion Video Lecture Live in-person workshop Nuggets Short quiz Learning materials and references</p>
<p>Cluster 3 Mindfulness Stress Management</p> <p>Inclusion Audio/Video Mindfulness Practices Pre-video handout, Post-video handout 4 mindfulness exercises with script 9 stress manage exercises with script</p>	<p>Cluster 4 Clinical Management of HIV/AIDS for Primary Care Providers</p> <p>Inclusion Video Lecture Video Vignettes Powerpoint slides Quizzes Learning materials and references</p>

Table 3. Content and Duration of Video Presentations

Cluster/Module Name	Content	Duration
Mental Health in HIV	HIV 101	23 Minutes-Video
	HIV and Mental Health	15 Minutes- Video
	Suicidality in HIV	70 Minutes- Video
	Metal Health Screening and Assessment	30 Minutes- Video
	Mental Health First AID	40 Minutes- Video
	SEEDS Factors	47 Minutes- Video
Motivational Interviewing	Introduction	60 Minutes- Video
	Fundamental Skills OARS	60 Minutes- Video
	Fundamental Skills Cont 1	66 Minutes- Video
	Fundamental Skills Cont 2	60 Minutes- Video
	Synchronous Session Recording	47 Minutes- Video Part 1 46 Minutes- Video Part 2
Self-care	Mindfulness 1 Breath Awareness	10 Minutes- Video
	Mindfulness 2 Three Steps Breathing Space	10 Minutes- Video
	Mindfulness 3 Body Scan	13 Minutes- Video
	Mindfulness 4 Mountain Meditation	13 Minutes- Video
	Stress Management 1 Self-compassion	11 Minutes- Video
	Stress Management 2 Body Scan and Breathing	15 Minutes- Video
	Stress Management 3 Giving and Receiving Compassion	12 Minutes- Video
	Stress Management 4 Affectionate Breathing	10 Minutes- Video

	Stress Management 5 Labelling Emotions	13 Minutes- Video
	Stress Management 6 Being with Difficult Emotions	13 Minutes- Video
	Stress Management 7 Loving Kindness for a Loved One	14 Minutes- Video
	Stress Management 8 Loving Kindness for Ourselves	10 Minutes- Video
	Stress Management 9 Seasons of the Heart	10 Minutes- Video
Clinical Management of HIV	HIV Etiology, Course, and Treatment Introduction	23 Minutes- Video
	HIV Treatment Hub Process	Client Initiated Testing - 7 Minutes Provider Initiated Testing and Counseling - 9 Minutes Getting Consent for a Comatose Patient - 5 Minutes Post-test Counseling - 23 Minutes Adherence Counseling - 18 Minutes

The first cluster: HIV and Mental Health

The first cluster is composed of HIV and Mental Health virtual modules. These modules aim to improve the knowledge of primary care providers on how mental health issues affect treatment outcomes and retention of PLHIVs. HIV 101 serves as an introduction to the module which aims to demystify common misconceptions of HIV by explaining how it develops (i.e. stages and symptomatology) and gets transmitted. HIV 101 also contains resources where PLHIVs in the Philippines can be referred for inpatient and outpatient treatment. The module then proceeds to provide primary care providers for PLHIVs with knowledge and resources on how to address mental health concerns that require immediate attention and screening. Quick screening tools (e.g. GAD-7, PHQ-9, and ASSIST) for common mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and suicidality are discussed. An overview of mental health first aid (MHFA) is provided supporting PLHIVs at risk for suicide, and practicing self-care through the lens of Brain-Based Therapy (i.e. SEEDS Factors)(Arden, 2014). This module provides a good backdrop to all succeeding modules, establishing the importance of mental health care in the HIV treatment continuum. Each module is anywhere between 60 minutes to 90 minutes.

The second cluster: Motivational Interviewing

This cluster aims to teach primary care providers ways how to build rapport and support PLHIVs that could facilitate change through the principles of Motivational Interviewing (MI). HIV is a lifelong condition and requires a good working relationship with care providers to ensure treatment adherence and retention. When trustworthiness and credibility are elicited during interaction, inputs become more influential in changing behavior. This is in line with motivational interviewing techniques where “care” is non-judgmental, respectful, and authentic. This module not only explains the principles of MI but also strives to help primary care providers

promote behavioral change while respecting their client's autonomy using the four fundamental skills in MI. Except for the in-person session which lasted for 3.5 hours, each virtual session was less than 60 minutes each.

The third cluster: Self-help Strategies

The third cluster consists of modules that provide health providers with self-help strategies. In the self-care strategies for primary care providers, two practice courses are offered: mindfulness (4 exercises) and stress-management practices (9 exercises). Duration of each practice session lasted for less than 10 minutes to 20 minutes. The cluster offers a menu of exercises for the participants to choose from.

The fourth cluster: Clinical Management of HIV

The fourth is a special cluster on the clinical management of HIV. The primary goal of this online training course is to provide primary care providers with the opportunity to improve their knowledge on the diagnosis, management and prevention of HIV disease and associated opportunistic infections. This course also provides a venue to enhance their skills and expertise regarding provision of primary care for HIV-infected patients, in coordination with colleagues, ancillary health providers and other stakeholders in a multidisciplinary care model. This cluster has the potential of being offered as a blended learning program combining a face-to-face session with asynchronous exercises.

Phase 3: Pre-Implementation Interviews

The interviews with experienced health HIV workers who lacked a formal background in mental health identified the factors that can contribute to the optimal utilization of the e-learning modules. There were six factors that were identified as critical in the acceptance and utilization of the e-modules. These were the learner's motivation, delivery and content of the modules, interaction with facilitators and co-learners, logistical advantage, personal barriers, and technical barriers (See Table 4).

The on-demand e-modules drew mixed reactions from the interviewees. Some viewed it positively. Motivation and discipline appear to be the key factors in their positive acceptance of the modules. All welcomed the continuing use of virtual modules but quite a number cited the advantage of using a blended method of presentation: a live face-to-face session using the module as a learning material that can be viewed inside or outside the in-person sessions. They preferred this approach because it allows for live interaction and guided discussion of questions and issues related to the topic, which according to them are important ingredients in effective training. Moreover, the dynamic process in face-to-face sessions was held by many as advantageous as it allows for immediate feedback on misunderstandings or misapplication of skills. The importance of monitoring and close supervision particularly in mental health counseling was highlighted. It was suggested that the passive nature of the online method should accommodate questions directed to the facilitator despite a delay in answering them.

Ironically, others were resisting the concept of independent e-learning because of time constraints. Technological reasons such as connectivity and competence in navigating online were also of high concern. They mentioned the sensitivity of the topic such as depression and suicidality as more appropriate for facilitator-guided discussion in a live masterclass.

On the question of how the modules could be used in HIV treatment hubs or social hygiene clinics, the role of the leader or head of the clinic was emphasized as crucial.

The organization of most clinics or treatment hubs is hierarchical where the physician holds the overall responsibility of managing its HR operations. It was suggested that this leader could either mandate the viewing as mandatory or he could encourage short learning sessions on special topics that integrate these e-modules.

Table 4 presents a detailed listing of the factors contributing to the acceptance of the modules and the barriers that make it a less attractive option.

Table 4. Summary of Underlying Themes and Sub-Themes

Themes	Sub-themes	Quotes
Motivation	Dedication	<i>If the person wants to learn, e-courses are as effective as in-person. (P1)</i>
	Short delivery	<i>If Less than 1 hour. (P2)</i>
	Leadership support	<i>It is helpful if supported by clinic head. (P3, P4)</i> <i>It can be required but there should be a follow-up to assess application. (P3, P1)</i>
	No time	<i>We are all busy (P6).</i> <i>I watch after clinic hours (P2)</i>
Delivery and Content	Synchronous watching	<i>It can be watched at the same time so they can discuss with the group. (P3)</i>
	Support with learning resources	<i>Add links since it is shorter (P2)</i>
	Structure of lecture	<i>Ideally, a step-by-step flowchart. (P3)</i>
	Sensitivity of topic	<i>Sensitive topics are better with live facilitators (P1)</i>
Communication	Cold medium	<i>No feelings. No connection being felt.(P4)</i>
	Limited interaction with the facilitator	<i>The facilitator must be available for Q&A. (P5)</i>
	Quick response of facilitator is key.	<i>Questions could not be answered immediately. (P5)</i>
	Face-to-face exercises are important.	<i>Faster session but less impact. Role playing is lost. (P5)</i>
	Quiet	<i>No noise. (P5)</i>
Advantage over in-person	Savings on logistics	<i>Cheaper. (P5)</i> <i>No need to travel and book accommodation. (P1)</i>
	Access to esteemed speakers	<i>Speakers who are difficult to bring to Philippines can give a lecture. (P1)</i>
	Flexibility	<i>I watch at home or after clinic. (P2)</i>
Barriers	Technical challenges if left alone.	<i>I am not techy. I prefer in-person because I am an "old school" person. (P5)</i>
	Risk of negative emotional response	<i>What if something in the (mental health) video triggered me? (P2)</i>
	Internet connectivity Device being used	<i>Signal could be a problem; unstable internet even here in Manila (P4).</i>

Discussion

In this study, we used three lenses to develop a deeper and holistic understanding of HIV and mental health, a much-neglected topic in our country. First is the lens provided by primary data that deals with the mental health situation among people infected with HIV in the Philippines. Such data provided a voice to hundreds of PLHIV who participated in the study. Second is getting the perspective of a team of interdisciplinary experts who designed the e-modules that aim to equip health workers with basic helping skills. Third, is soliciting the opinion of health workers on the acceptability of on-demand e-learning modules on mental health and HIV. Three perspectives that assisted in bridging HIV and mental health with a particular focus on healthcare providers, were attempted by this study.

The data from the mental health survey we conducted show that mental health and psychosocial problems such as stigma remain a problem among PLHIV. At the time of the survey, participants were visiting their HIV doctors for medical monitoring and follow-up. It comes as a surprise that 1 out of 4 were experiencing depression and anxiety; and contemplated suicide. It is plausible that many remain untreated for these mental problems or are hardly referred for these conditions. This is an area that needs further investigation. There is a big challenge ahead of us on how to close this gap. However, there are small and isolated steps being undertaken to address this problem. There are intervention campaigns to integrate valid screening psychological instruments in clinical settings to raise awareness among health workers on the prevalence of specific mental conditions in their clinics. There is an emerging conversation in scientific meetings on the feasibility of a collaborative model of treatment against the integrative model. The collaborative model relies on an active networking of disciplines such as psychiatry and clinical psychology, to name a few. It has been asserted that the integrative model demands policy changes and organizational challenges. The acquisition of resources i.e. creating permanent positions, makes this model subject to potential argumentation and resistance. On the whole, institutionalizing mental health services entails hard work in terms of reaching out and achieving mutual interest among the different specialists outside of HIV treatment hubs.

Currently, health workers continue to advocate the traditional in-person training methods with e-training as a secondary option. Unlike the traditional mode, motivation is a crucial factor in the latter method— either as an individual learner or as someone following the orders of the group leader. According to their views, in-person training builds not only skills but attitudes that foster confidence and awareness in helping patients with mental or emotional issues. Acquiring helping skills online can lead to good knowledge but it can be lacking in practice and application. Hence, a combination of deductive and inductive approaches in face-to-face training with close supervision and coaching of trainees seemed to be the ideal method; and using online resources as a supplement.

The culture of online learning among health workers needs to be embedded for online education and training to flourish in the country. We are inspired by several international studies that have reported positive e-learning outcomes, a few of which have demonstrated equal impact comparable to face-to-face training (Karing, 2023; Sommers-Spikerman et al. 2021; White et al, 2019; Paechter & Maier, 2010;). As facilitators, we have yet to learn on the technology of innovative online learning in terms of how to enhance participation and interaction (Pachter & Maier, 2010); how to apply principles learned; and how to keep the full attention and focus of learners.

Meanwhile, the utilization of online programs is hampered by local interferences such as unstable internet and poor signals. Even if the internet is stable, overburdened health workers complain of physical exhaustion and availability when they reach home.

The next step that we endeavor to do is to pilot test a suitable approach for using the e-modules. One condition is to set up an in-person training on a particular topic, incorporating the e-module as a learning material for discussion. The second condition is to provide a live e-training where participants can post questions and the facilitator provides immediate feedback on the live module that has been watched. The third is a pure e-module approach or pure audio approach. These three different conditions can be compared in terms of cognitive understanding and learner satisfaction. The systematic study of the three learning modalities has been previously conducted outside the Philippines (Ebner & Gegenfurtner, 2019; Kaufman, et al, 2021; Olson et al, 2019; White et al, 2019). However, the interest of the researchers will be finding out the cognitive and motivational appeal of each of these modalities among local health workers given their background and culture.

Conclusion

We learned from this 2-year research project the importance of generating awareness and activating enthusiasm in 3 areas namely: relevance, motivation, and a wider spectrum of care. The relevance should be data-driven and it should be disseminated as widely as possible to inform a range of audiences from policymakers to clinic managers to counselors and patients. Internal and external sources of learning motivation about HIV and mental health should be recognized as the key to successful learning outcomes. Finally, the enhancement of the role of health workers in mental health must receive training support and encouragement from leaders and clinic heads in order to take off. There is now a rich menu of training modalities to choose from which makes skills and knowledge upgrades more accessible and less costly.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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